

THE POLITICAL ECONOMY OF EXCISE TAXATION: SOME ETHICAL AND LEGAL ISSUES

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Abstract

Excise taxes are used not only to raise revenue but also to alter or punish behavior. In many cases, excise taxes can be called "sin" taxes because they punish people for politically incorrect behavior like smoking and consuming alcoholic beverages. This article examines the nonrevenue raising uses of excise taxes and analyzes their propriety from the perspectives of economics, law and ethics.

Introduction

Some of the content of this paper is based on Chapter 1 of Shughart's book on excise taxes.² Shughart's book is one of the few books that takes a critical look at the nonrevenue raising aspects of excise taxes. Thus, it is a good starting point for a discussion of how excise taxes have gone astray from their revenue raising function.

The Economics of the Nanny State

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² TAXING CHOICE: THE PREDATORY POLITICS OF FISCAL DISCRIMINATION (WILLIAM F. SHUGHART, II, ED., 1997).

Excise taxes are no longer imposed just to raise revenue. In fact, it is becoming increasingly likely that those who advocate imposing or raising excise taxes only pay lip service to the revenue raising aspect. The real goal is often to further some politically correct agenda. That certainly seems to be the case for taxes on alcohol, tobacco and firearms. The government's fiscal function has come to devote increased resources to punishing or regulating behavior rather than raising revenue.

Traditionally, those who advocate excise taxes have used three economic justifications.³ One justification is the so-called *Ramsey Rule*,⁴ which advocates taxing commodities based on their elasticities of demand. Commodities like alcohol and tobacco are highly inelastic, meaning that most people who purchase these products will continue to do so regardless of cost. So it becomes feasible to slap on an excise tax since doing so will not result in reducing demand very much. Supposedly, applying this rule results in minimizing the excess burden of taxation and minimizing social cost.

The second rationale is based on the concept of a user fee. User fees are not really taxes, in a sense, since the only people who pay them are the ones who use the service. This tends to be true in the case of the excise tax on gasoline, provided the revenues generated from the tax are used to support highway maintenance and construction. This line of reasoning has recently been extended to alcohol, tobacco and firearms to justify increasing the tax to pay for alcohol abuse treatment centers, cancer research, and so forth.

³ SHUGHART, *supra*, discusses these three justifications at 13-14. On the subject of justification of taxation, see Walter Block, *The Justification for Taxation in the Economics Literature*, in THE ETHICS OF TAX EVASION 36-88 (ROBERT W. MCGEE, ED., 1998). Block reviewed the economics literature and failed to find a single justification for taxation that would stand up to close analysis.

⁴ For discussions of the Ramsey Rule, see HARVEY S. ROSEN, PUBLIC FINANCE 310-314, 318 (5TH ED. 1999); JOHN CULLIS AND PHILIP JONES, PUBLIC FINANCE AND PUBLIC CHOICE, 376, 380-381 (2ND ED. 1998); MICHAEL L. MARLOW, PUBLIC FINANCE: THEORY AND PRACTICE 455-456 (1995).

The third argument that has been put forth for selective excise taxation is to correct something that some politicians, government bureaucrats or special interest group (usually consisting of do-gooders) think needs correcting. In economic language, one might say that excise taxes could be used to internalize externalities,⁵ or to push up the cost to the consumer to equal the total social cost in cases where the purchase price of this or that product does not cover the total social cost.⁶

Selective Taxes and the Ramsey Rule

Excise taxes have been criticized for violating both the vertical equity rule and the horizontal equity rule,⁷ which leads one to wonder why they exist.⁸ Those who criticize excise taxes for violating vertical equity do so because of the belief that excise taxes fall disproportionately on the poor, whereas they should fall disproportionately on the rich, since the rich are better able to pay.

While not taking the position that excise taxes are equitable, I question whether the fact that if excise taxes are

⁵ For some discussions of internalizing externalities from a Public Choice perspective, see J.M. Buchanan and W.C. Stubblebine, *Externality*, 29 *ECONOMICA* 371-384 (1962); J.M. Buchanan, *External Diseconomies, Corrective Taxes and Market Structure*, 59 *AMERICAN ECONOMIC REVIEW* 174-177 (1969).

⁶ There are a number of problems with the concept of "social cost," since all costs are, in reality, individual costs. Space does not permit a full treatment of this concept. For one critique of the concept of social cost, see S.N.S. Cheung, *The Myth of Social Cost*, Hobart Paper No 82 (London: Institute of Economic Affairs, 1978). For the classic discussion on the problem of social cost, see Ronald H. Coase, *The Problem of Social Cost*, 3 *JOURNAL OF LAW AND ECONOMICS* 1-44 (1960).

⁷ For discussions of vertical and horizontal equity, see HARVEY S. ROSEN, *PUBLIC FINANCE* 313, 323-326 (5TH ED. 1999); JOHN CULLIS AND PHILIP JONES, *PUBLIC FINANCE AND PUBLIC CHOICE*, 9, 398 (2ND ED. 1998); MICHAEL L. MARLOW, *PUBLIC FINANCE: THEORY AND PRACTICE* 423-425, 561 (1995); DAVID N. HYMAN, *PUBLIC FINANCE: A CONTEMPORARY APPLICATION OF THEORY TO POLICY* 380 (6TH ED., 1999).

⁸ SHUGHART, *supra*, at 14.

regressive that is necessarily bad,⁹ since lower income groups might derive disproportionate benefits from the proceeds collected from excise taxes. If that is the case, it seems that lower income groups should pay more than those in higher income categories, since they derive more benefit from the taxes.

Another problem with the premise that the ability to pay principle should be used to determine whether excise taxes violate vertical equity is the fact that the ability to pay principle is ethically bankrupt.¹⁰ There are only two ways to look at the relationship between government and the people. Either the government is the master and the people are the servants or the government is the servant and the people are the masters.¹¹ The ability to pay principle has as its premise the view that government is the master and the rich are to be exploited merely because they

⁹ Provided there can be such a thing as a good tax. We will leave discussion of that point for another day. Almost all writers in the area of public finance begin with the presumption that there can be such a thing as a good tax. The problem with this view is that all taxes rely on coercion, which violates the nonaggression axiom -- the starting point of moral philosophy. For more on the nonaggression axiom, see MURRAY N. ROTHBARD, *FOR A NEW LIBERTY* 23-26 (REV. ED. 1978). Adam Smith discussed good taxes and bad taxes in *THE WEALTH OF NATIONS* (1776). Lord Henry Home Kames listed six rules to be observed in taxing in his *SKETCHES ON THE HISTORY OF MAN* (1769). The tax ideas of these two scholars are discussed in CHARLES ADAMS, *FOR GOOD AND EVIL: THE IMPACT OF TAXES ON THE COURSE OF CIVILIZATION* 286-287 (1993).

¹⁰ For more on this point, see Robert W. McGee, *The Case for a Maximum Tax: A Look at Some Legal, Economic and Ethical Issues*, 1 *JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING, ETHICS & PUBLIC POLICY* 294-299 (Spring 1998); Robert W. McGee, *Is the Ability to Pay Principle Ethically Bankrupt?* 1 *JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING, ETHICS & PUBLIC POLICY* (Summer 1998); Robert W. McGee, *Are Discriminatory Tax Rates Ethically Justifiable?* 1 *JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING, ETHICS & PUBLIC POLICY* (Fall 1998); Robert W. McGee, *Should Rich People Pay More than Poor People? An Ethical Look at the Graduated Income Tax*, *COMMENTARIES ON THE LAW OF ACCOUNTING & FINANCE* (1998).

¹¹ This point is discussed in more depth in Robert W. McGee, *Some Tax Advice for Latvia and Other Similarly Situated Emerging Economies*, 13 *INTERNATIONAL TAX & BUSINESS LAWYER* 223-308 (1996), at 233-234.

(supposedly)¹² are better able to pay for the cost of government. The ability to pay principle ignores the basic rule of fairness that taxpayers should receive benefits more or less in proportion to what they pay in taxes.¹³

Another view of fairness within the public finance literature is horizontal equity, the belief that people who make about the same amount of income should pay about the same amount of taxes. The fact is that they often do not. Rich people who do not smoke do not pay any excise taxes on cigarettes, for example.¹⁴ But so what?

¹² This view relies on the belief that each marginal unit of income is less needed than previous income units. The problem is that it is impossible to measure such things. Even if it were possible to measure the relative pain of taking an additional monetary unit from a rich man versus a poor man, it does not logically follow that it should be done. To logically conclude such an action is to fall prey to a non sequitur.

¹³ It is impossible to precisely match benefits received with the amount of taxes paid. The only way to match payments and benefits would be to completely eliminate taxes and let people pay for all services through the market, which could provide just about everything cheaper and more efficiently than government anyway. For more on this point, see RANDALL FITZGERALD, *WHEN GOVERNMENT GOES PRIVATE: SUCCESSFUL ALTERNATIVES TO PUBLIC SERVICES* (1988); MADSEN PIRIE, *PRIVATIZATION IN THEORY AND PRACTICE* (1985).

Another problem with attempting to measure the cost of government with the benefits received is due to the fact that people are forced to pay for government services, many of which they would not purchase if they had a choice. Who in his right mind, for example, would voluntarily pay for Social Security, when just about every mutual fund that ever existed would provide a better investment vehicle? For a moral treatment of Social Security, see Robert W. McGee, *The Economics and Ethics of Abolishing Social Security*, 1 *JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING, ETHICS & PUBLIC POLICY* 300-305 (Spring 1998).

¹⁴ That is not to say that rich people who do not smoke do not have their standard of living reduced just because they do not pay excise taxes. Everyone, smoker and nonsmoker alike, has their standard of living reduced because smokers have to pay excise taxes. That is because the money used to pay excise taxes cannot be used to purchase services and products that the market would otherwise provide. A rich, nonsmoking tailor, for example, might not be able to sell a suit to a smoker because the smoker has to pay hundreds of dollars each year in excise taxes, making it impossible to buy the suit due to lack of available

Excise taxes are far from neutral. They have at least three effects. They reduce the supply of whatever commodity or service is taxed, they raise its price and they modify its attributes.¹⁵ In the case of cigarettes, for example, excise taxes can influence the color of the wrapper, the length of the cigarette, the blend of tobacco and the amount of tar and nicotine. That is because the amount of excise tax can be different for different characteristics. Those characteristics that receive relatively favorable tax treatment will tend to be supplied.¹⁶ In the case of cigarettes, for example, the excise tax can cause long cigarettes to become more attractive than short cigarettes,¹⁷ which is the exact opposite of what the anti-tobacco do-gooders probably intended.¹⁸

One reason, perhaps the main one, why cigarettes and alcoholic beverages sold outside the United States tend to be stronger than those sold in the United States is because other countries charge much higher excise taxes on these products.¹⁹ High tax rates have a tendency to increase potency.

funds. The tailor cannot spend the money he does not receive to go on a vacation, which would benefit the waiters at his favorite Miami Beach restaurant, etc. This relationship between what is seen and what is not seen -- direct and indirect effects -- was pointed out by Frederic Bastiat in France in the 1840s. For a more modern treatment, see HENRY HAZLITT, *ECONOMICS IN ONE LESSON* (1946).

¹⁵ RICHARD E. WAGNER, *PUBLIC FINANCE: REVENUES AND EXPENDITURES IN A DEMOCRATIC SOCIETY* 259 (1983), as cited in SHUGHART, *supra*, at 14.

¹⁶ This phenomenon is merely an application of the Alchian and Allen theorem, "which shows how fixed costs can affect the relative prices of low- and high-quality products." SHUGHART, *supra*, at 15. For the theorem, see ARMEN A. ALCHIAN AND WILLIAM R. ALLEN, *UNIVERSITY ECONOMICS* 63-64 (2ND ED., 1967), as cited in SHUGHART, *supra*, at 15.

¹⁷ For more detail on this point, see SHUGHART, *supra*, at 15.

¹⁸ For an extensive exposé on do-gooders in general and how they are destroying freedom in America, see JAMES T. BENNETT AND THOMAS J. DILORENZO, *THE FOOD AND DRINK POLICE: AMERICA'S NANNIES, BUSYBODIES & PETTY TYRANTS* (1999).

¹⁹ SHUGHART, *supra*, at 15. It might also be pointed out that our idiotic war on drugs is responsible for increasing the potency of the illegal drugs that are now

Increasing excise taxes also decreases social welfare, since an increase in price causes consumers to shift their purchases to products that previously ranked lower on their list of preferences.

...because the tax inserts a "wedge" between the amount paid by the consumer and the after-tax amount received by the producer, a "deadweight" welfare loss is also imposed on society. This loss is called a deadweight loss because its value is transferred away from market participants but is not captured by the government or anyone else. This deadweight welfare loss is also referred to as the "excess burden" of the tax because it represents the amount by which the value of the welfare losses imposed on producers and consumers exceeds the revenue collected by the tax authority.²⁰

The *Ramsey Rule* holds that placing excise taxes on products in inverse proportion to their elasticities of demand is the way to minimize the excess tax burden.²¹ In other words, governments should charge high excise taxes on products where consumers will not reduce their consumption by much and low excise taxes on products where consumers will reduce their purchases if excise taxes are raised. This rule provides the intellectual justification for placing heavy excise taxes on alcohol and tobacco.²²

The *Ramsey Rule* has been criticized on at least three counts.²³ For one, there is little evidence to support the belief that

available. Drugs are easier to find and confiscate if they are bulky. The solution is to deliver a product that is less bulky but just as potent. That is why crack cocaine has replaced powdered cocaine.

²⁰ SHUGHART, *supra*, at 16.

²¹ SHUGHART, *supra*, at 17.

²² SHUGHART, *supra*, at 17.

²³ SHUGHART, *supra*, at 17.

government is motivated to maximize the efficiency of the tax code and much evidence to support the belief that efficiency has little or nothing to do with tax policy. Secondly, the rule assumes that government has as its goal the collection of some predetermined amount of tax revenue, whereas the actual goal of most governments seems to be collecting the maximum in taxes. Finally, the government imposes "sin" taxes to reduce consumption, while the *Ramsey Rule* would impose higher taxes because of the belief that consumption is not affected much because of the highly inelastic demand for products like alcohol and tobacco. Thus, the revenue-raising reasons and the regulatory reasons for high excise taxes work at cross purposes.

User Fees

A user fee, properly applied, is not really a tax, in the sense that coercion is not involved in collecting it. One can avoid paying the fee by not using the service or product. People can avoid paying the user fee that would be charged for admission to a government owned park by not entering the park.²⁴

Ideally,²⁵ the proceeds used from the collection of a user fee are earmarked²⁶ to pay for the service provided. The excise tax

²⁴ Why government owned parks should exist is another question, since there is much evidence to suggest that the private sector could do a better job of providing this kind of consumer good at a much lower cost. We will save discussion of this point for another day.

²⁵ For a discussion of optimal user fees, see Harvey S. Rosen, *Public Finance* 315-318 (5th Ed. 1999). For a detailed discussion of optimal taxation in general, see JOHN CULLIS AND PHILIP JONES, *PUBLIC FINANCE AND PUBLIC CHOICE*, 374-409 (2ND ED. 1998).

²⁶ Knut Wicksell, the economist who had great influence on Nobel Prizewinner James Buchanan, suggested that all taxes be earmarked. See Knut Wicksell, *Finanztheoretische Untersuchungen* (1896), reprinted as *A New Principle of Just Taxation*, In *CLASSICS IN THE THEORY OF PUBLIC FINANCE* 72-118 (RICHARD A. MUSGRAVE AND ALAN T. PEACOCK, EDS., 1958), as cited in SHUGHART, *supra*, at 29. The problem with earmarked taxes is that they are often used to supplement taxes from the general fund rather than to replace them. Thus, the total tax burden is increased. Therefore, earmarking taxes is best accomplished

on gasoline is used to maintain and construct highways. The tax on airline tickets is used to maintain airports.²⁷ Ideally, an excise tax should be charged by public schools so that only the parents of the children attending the school would have to pay for their education.²⁸

Unfortunately, the concept of user fees breaks down when it is actually applied. Earmarked taxes are highly fungible. If a state lottery raises funds for education, the state legislature (perhaps) reduces the amount of funding from the general fund without actually reducing tax rates, so the total tax burden increases. The user fee concept also breaks down as the ultimate use of the funds becomes distant from the funding source.

For example, suppose that the tax on alcohol and tobacco is increased to pay for Medicare and Medicaid. Smokers and drinkers benefit from Medicare and Medicaid but so do nonsmokers and nondrinkers. So some segment of the population is being forced to pay for benefits that another segment of the population receives.²⁹ Furthermore, some smokers and drinkers do not use Medicare or Medicaid, even though they are being forced to pay for these programs. At this point the concept of a user fee no longer applies.

when the earmarked taxes are the only taxes used to fund a particular service. Other taxes should be reduced by the amount of funds raised by earmarked taxes. Unfortunately, this approach is seldom taken.

²⁷ It is questionable why government should be involved in owning or maintaining airports. Several studies by the Reason Foundation point out the fact that the market does a better job of providing service in this area. See <http://www.reason.com>.

²⁸ For more on the privatization of education, see Robert W. McGee, *Brown v. Board of Education: Forty Years of Asking the Wrong Question & the Case for Privatization of Education*, ST. LOUIS UNIVERSITY PUBLIC LAW REVIEW, forthcoming. A number of studies have found that private schools can provide a better education at one-third to one-half the cost of public schools. For more on this point, see SHELDON RICHMAN, *SEPARATING SCHOOL AND STATE: HOT TO LIBERATE AMERICA'S FAMILIES* (1995).

²⁹ This fact is pointed out in SHUGHART, *supra*, at 20.

Another criticism of taxes on alcohol and tobacco is that they transfer wealth from the poor to the middle class.

Federal health care reform was marketed as an entitlement program for the middle class. Yet the consumers of alcohol and tobacco are disproportionately young and poor. As such, proposals for earmarking selective tax revenues to finance government health care programs are political ruses that serve to disguise a transfer of wealth from the lower end of the income distribution to the middle.³⁰

Internalizing Externalities & Corrective Taxes

One rationale for increasing certain excise taxes is because of the belief that the price of certain products, like alcohol and tobacco, does not cover the total cost. For example, when someone purchases cigarettes, he pays only for the cost of the cigarettes, not for the cost of curing or treating his cancer, which will not be incurred for a few decades. When someone buys an alcoholic beverage, the price he pays reflects merely the cost of providing the product, including some profit margin. It does not include the cost of providing alcohol abuse facilities. Thus, the total cost is not captured in the selling price, so excise taxes have to be increased to make up the difference. Economists would call this internalizing the externalities. Externalities are costs or benefits that are not reflected in the purchase price.

There are several problems with this rationale for slapping on excise taxes to internalize the negative externalities. The most obvious problem is that not everyone gets cancer from smoking and not all drinkers need the services of an alcohol abuse center. So all smokers are forced to pay for the services that only some smokers receive and all drinkers are forced to pay for services that only some drinkers receive.

³⁰ SHUGHART, *supra*, at 20.

Another problem with this rationale is that many people who take advantage of cancer treatment facilities are nonsmokers. It cannot be said that only smokers get cancer because many people who never smoked also get cancer.

Another, less obvious question, is why government should provide cancer treatment or alcohol abuse treatment facilities. These facilities can be provided through the market. Those who need the services can pay for them and those who do not need to use these facilities should not be forced to pay for them. Private insurance can be used to pay for these services, as can private savings. There is no need to for people to pay taxes for something that can be provided better and cheaper by the market.

Those who advocate the use of selective excise taxes to remedy this imbalance between private costs and social costs begin with the premise that there are "social" costs associated with the consumption of tobacco and alcohol products. The problem with this premise is that, upon closer examination, these "social" costs ultimately become private costs.³¹

Productivity losses, for example, are losses incurred by individuals, not society at large. Individuals who are absent from work because of tobacco and alcohol consumption lose pay and receive lower salary increases than would be the case if they did not consume these items. It is individuals who pay the price, not the general public. Those who perform at a substandard level because of consumption of these products tend to lose their jobs.

³¹ For more on this point, see William F. Shughart, II, *The Economics of the Nanny State*, in TAXING CHOICE: THE PREDATORY POLITICS OF FISCAL DISCRIMINATION 13-29 (WILLIAM F. SHUGHART, II, ED. 1997), at 20-24; Richard E. Wagner, *The Taxation of Alcohol and the Control of Social Costs*, in TAXING CHOICE: THE PREDATORY POLITICS OF FISCAL DISCRIMINATION 227-246 (WILLIAM F. SHUGHART, II, ED. 1997); Paula A. Gant and Robert B. Ekelund, Jr., *Excise Taxes, Social Costs, and the Consumption of Wine*, In TAXING CHOICE: THE PREDATORY POLITICS OF FISCAL DISCRIMINATION 247-269 (WILLIAM F. SHUGHART, II, ED. 1997).

Again, it is individuals, not society, who incur the cost. There is no externality to internalize.³²

Which brings us to another point. Since there is no externality to internalize, why increase excise taxes? If the purpose of having selective excise taxes is to internalize externalities, it seems like excise taxes are not called for where there are no externalities to internalize.

The argument has been made that nonsmokers are harmed by cigarette smoke in the workplace. Thus, it follows that they should be compensated. However, studies have shown³³ that nonsmokers tend to be compensated more than nonsmokers in terms of long-term salary, so they are already being compensated. Again, costs that were previously labeled as "social" costs have been shown to be individual costs.

Another aspect of the compensation problem, one that has been neglected in the literature, is the beneficial economic effects of smoking and drinking. If smokers and drinkers die sooner than the general population, they will use less Medicare and Medicaid services than the average population. Thus, they will be less of a drain on these systems. They will also take less from the Social Security fund, thus leaving more for others. These are all positive externalities. The logical inference would be that smokers and drinkers should be compensated for these positive externalities, yet no one ever advocates that such policies be implemented. However, it should be pointed out that these costs are individual, not social costs. The rationale for compensating smokers and drinkers is based on the premise that these costs are social costs, when in fact they are not.

Concluding Comments

Some studies that attempt to measure the "social" cost of smoking and drinking conclude that excise taxes are already more than high enough to compensate others for the social costs of

³² SHUGHART, *supra*, discusses these points at 21-24.

³³ Some of these studies are cited in SHUGHART, *supra*, at 22.

smoking and drinking.³⁴ Thus, even if we begin with the faulty premise that there are social costs associated with smoking and drinking, it appears that there is no need to increase excise taxes, since the present level of taxation is sufficient to pay for these alleged "social" costs. Of course, when one recognizes the fact that most or all of the costs that were called social costs in the past are actually individual costs that are already accounted for, it leads to the conclusion that existing excise taxes on alcohol and tobacco products should be repealed.

Repealing such taxes will not have the effect of increasing consumption, since the demand curves for alcohol and tobacco products are highly inelastic.³⁵ One beneficial effect of abolishing excise taxes on alcohol and tobacco products would be that their potency would likely decrease, since there is a positive correlation between the level of excise taxes and the potency of the product. Thus, abolishing excise taxes would result in a more healthy population.

Another beneficial effect of abolishing excise taxes is that consumers would have more money in their pockets to spend on other products and services. The deadweight loss that always is present where there are excise taxes would no longer be present. The economy would operate more efficiently and all segments of the market would expand as the demand curves for their products and services shift to the right.

The bottom line is that there is no ethical reason to have excise taxes on alcohol and tobacco products. All costs associated with these products are individual, not social costs. There are no externalities to internalize. It is not a legitimate function of government to punish people for engaging in activities that are none of the government's business, like smoking and drinking. The only legitimate functions of government are to protect the lives and

³⁴ Some of these studies are cited in SHUGHART, *supra*, at 24.

³⁵ Even if consumption did increase, it is no concern of government, since it is not a legitimate function of government to regulate individual non-rights-violating behavior.

property of the people who pay taxes. It is never a legitimate function of government to protect people from themselves.